

Empowering Faculty in the Era of GAI: Toward Responsible Implementation in Higher Education

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Abstract

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) represents one of the most significant changes in the contemporary educational landscape. This article proposes a conceptual framework for the responsible implementation of GAI in higher education, centered on faculty empowerment as the articulating axis of the educational transformation process. Through a mixed methodological approach that combines documentary analysis and structured surveys applied to faculty from a School of Education, a decalogue of fundamental principles was developed that seeks to balance technological innovation with the preservation of human value in education. Results reveal that although a considerable number of faculty already use GAI tools, there is ample room for improvement in understanding and effective application of these technologies. Key areas of attention identified include technological dependence, data privacy, and the need for clear policies that facilitate ethical and effective use of GAI in educational contexts.

Keywords: Generative Artificial Intelligence, higher education, faculty empowerment, educational transformation, educational ethics, digital literacy

Introduction

For centuries, education has been conceptualized as a fundamentally human, situated, and ethical act. However, the emergence of Generative Artificial Intelligence in classrooms has raised profound questions about the future of educational practice. The central question is not whether GAI will transform education—as it is already doing so—but how we can accompany this change without diluting the essential role of the educator.

This article argues that the key to successful implementation of GAI in higher education lies in faculty empowerment, understood not as the simple incorporation of technological tools, but as an integral process of training, support, and recognition of the educator as a designer of meaningful learning experiences. This perspective aligns with critical approaches that emphasize the need to maintain human agency in technology-mediated educational processes (Selwyn 2023, 45-62).

The urgency of this discussion is based on the unprecedented speed with which GAI has been integrated into educational contexts. Since the launch of ChatGPT in November 2022, higher education institutions have faced

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the need to develop policies, ethical frameworks, and pedagogical strategies to respond to this technological transformation (García-Peñalvo 2024, 12-18). This response cannot be reactive or improvised; it requires a systematic and empirically grounded approach that places faculty at the center of the change process.

Conceptual framework: from replacement to empowerment

The discussion about GAI in education has oscillated between two equally problematic extremes: categorical rejection based on technophobia and uncritical adoption based on technological determinism. Both positions ignore a fundamental reality: technology, by itself, does not determine educational outcomes; it is its contextualized and ethically oriented implementation that defines its impact (O'Neil 2016, 78-95).

The concept of faculty empowerment proposed here transcends mere technical training. It implies the recognition of the educator as a critical professional, capable of evaluating, adapting, and integrating GAI tools in a manner consistent with their pedagogical objectives and institutional context. This approach is distinguished from the predominant discourse that presents AI as a universal technological solution, ignoring the contextual and cultural specificities of educational processes (Benjamin 2019, 134-156).

The faculty empowerment perspective is based on three conceptual pillars derived from literature analysis and empirical evidence collected: professional autonomy, critical competence, and ethical responsibility. Professional autonomy implies that faculty must maintain control over fundamental pedagogical decisions, using GAI as a tool that amplifies their capabilities without substituting their professional judgment. Critical competence requires the development of skills to evaluate, question, and adapt emerging technologies. Ethical responsibility demands that educators consider the moral and social implications of their technological decisions.

Dimensions of the conceptual framework

Following the model proposed by La Salle University in its Formative Approach, the responsible implementation of GAI is structured in three fundamental dimensions that organize both analysis and policy proposals:

Cognitive dimension: Focuses on how GAI can support and extend thinking and learning capabilities without replacing human judgment. This dimension emphasizes that technology should facilitate deeper and more personalized understanding processes, while maintaining critical thinking and human interaction as central elements of the educational process (Buckingham Shum and Ferguson 2012, 3-26).

Ethical dimension: Addresses emerging ethical challenges of GAI use, including privacy, informed consent, and possibility of algorithmic biases. This dimension underscores the importance of transparency and accountability as fundamental principles, aligning with the need to form individuals' conscious of their social and technological impact (Mittelstadt et al. 2016, 1-21).

Social dimension: Considers the impact of GAI on the educational community and society in general. This dimension promotes a vision of education that transcends the functional, focusing on integral formation and collective well-being, ensuring that technology serves as a bridge and not as a barrier within the educational community (Floridi et al. 2018, 689-707).

Methodology

This research employs a mixed methodological design that combines documentary analysis with empirical

research through structured surveys. This multidimensional approach allows for the collection of robust data that integrates quantitative and qualitative perspectives to analyze the ethical and effective implementation of GAI in higher education.

Population and sample

The target population consisted of permanent faculty from the School of Education of a Latin American university. A sample equivalent to 95% of the expected population (N=30) was achieved, guaranteeing statistical representativeness and validity of the results obtained.

Data collection instruments

Structured survey: An eight-question questionnaire was designed and validated that combines closed items to obtain quantitative data and open items to capture detailed perceptions and personal explanations. The instrument was validated by colleagues from the research group following established protocols for educational research (Fowler 2013).

The questionnaire explored four main dimensions:

- Level of knowledge about GAI and its application in education
- Previous experience with GAI tools in teaching practice
- Ethical perceptions about challenges associated with AI use in education
- Aspects considered essential for institutional policies on ethical AI use

Documentary review: Institutional documents, academic publications, and policy guides were analyzed to obtain in-depth understanding of current standards and recommended practices in GAI use in higher education. This process included the collection and study of relevant literature to theoretically ground the study (Hart 2018).

Analysis process

Findings from structured surveys and documentary review were synthesized to develop policy recommendations on ethical and effective implementation of GAI in higher education. An integrated analysis was employed that combines quantitative data from surveys with qualitative insights from open responses and reviewed documents (Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña 2014).

Results of empirical research

Knowledge and use of GAI

Results of the applied questionnaire revealed significant data about the current state of knowledge and use of GAI among university faculty:

Level of knowledge: 40% of participants indicated having no knowledge about generative artificial intelligence and its application in education, while 57% expressed having some general notion of the topic.

Practical experience: Of the 57% who expressed having knowledge, 43.3% had previously used GAI tools in their teaching practice, while 56.7% had not had practical experience with these technologies.

Specific applications: Among those who use GAI, 35% employed it in research class development, 20% in rubric creation, 15% in presentations, 15% in linking with bibliographic references, and 15% indicated using ChatGPT without specific function.

Ethical perceptions

Analysis of ethical perceptions revealed consensus about the importance of considering ethical challenges in GAI use:

Ethical relevance: All participants indicated some level of relevance to ethical challenges suggested by UNESCO for GAI use in education; more than 80% considered ethical consideration fundamental.

Main challenges identified:

Technological dependence and loss of critical or creative skills: 64.3% Privacy and

security of student and teacher data: 56.7%

Equity in access to AI technologies: 56.7%

Transparency and explainability of processes: 50% Algorithmic biases

and discrimination: 36.7%

Knowledge of institutional policies

Only 10% of those consulted claimed to know any policy on ethical AI use at their institution, revealing a significant gap between the need for guidance and availability of clear normative frameworks.

Priority aspects for institutional policies

Participants identified the following aspects as essential for institutional policies on ethical AI use:

Academic integrity: 76.7%

Continuous professional development: 76.7%

Informed consent: 70%

Privacy and data protection: 60% Transparency and

accountability: 60% Equitable access: 46.7%

Equity and non-discrimination: 40%

Environmental impact: 40% Collective work

and feedback: 3.3%

Analysis of specialized literature

Documentary review identified seven key areas in which GAI policies in higher education are concentrated, confirming the need for a comprehensive and systematic approach:

Ethics and accountability

There is a growing consensus on the need to develop policies that ensure ethical use of AI in universities. This includes implementation of principles of transparency, equity, and accountability to prevent bias and discrimination (Fjeld et al. 2020).

Curricular integration of AI

Guidelines should address how AI is integrated into university curricula, including not only the use of AI tools to improve teaching and learning processes, but also student training in AI-related competencies (Jobin, Ienca,

and Vayena 2019, 389-399).

Interdisciplinary collaboration

Findings highlight the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in AI policy development, including cooperation between technology experts, educators, psychologists, and ethics specialists (Crawford and Calo 2016, 311-313).

Accessibility and inclusion

A critical area is ensuring that AI tools and systems are accessible to all learners, including those with disabilities, promoting inclusion and avoiding perpetuation of existing inequalities (Whittaker et al. 2018).

Governance and continuous updating

Given the accelerated pace of development in the AI field, it is crucial that policies be regularly reviewed and updated to adapt to new technologies and emerging challenges (Vinuesa et al. 2020, 1-10).

Impact assessment and continuous feedback

It is vital to implement evaluation and feedback mechanisms to monitor AI's impact on the educational environment, including evaluation of how AI affects learning outcomes and overall student experience (Vinuesa et al. 2020, 1-10).

Preparation for automation

Policies should consider how AI could change the future of work and prepare students for these changes, including development of skills that AI cannot easily replicate (Whittaker et al. 2018).

Decalogue for responsible implementation of GAI

Based on empirical results obtained and analysis of specialized literature, the following decalogue is proposed that integrates the three conceptual dimensions identified (cognitive, ethical, and social) with specific needs detected in the studied educational context:

Promote AI literacy

It is fundamental that students, faculty, and administrative staff understand basic AI concepts, applications, limitations, and ethical and social implications of its use. This includes the ability to critically evaluate AI-generated content.

Empirical justification: Results show that 40% of faculty lack knowledge about GAI, while only 57% have general notions, evidencing urgent need for structured literacy programs.

Practical implementation: Development of training programs that include fundamental concepts, specific disciplinary applications, and supervised practice with GAI tools (Galindo Cuesta 2024).

Train faculty specifically and contextually

Educators must be equipped to effectively use GAI tools and guide students in their appropriate and ethical use. This implies an evolution of the teaching role toward a facilitator of AI-mediated learning experiences, with new competencies in prompt engineering and critical evaluation.

Empirical justification: 76.7% of surveyed faculty considered continuous professional development essential, confirming demand for specialized training programs.

Practical implementation: Design of professional development programs that include technical competencies (prompt engineering), pedagogical competencies (curricular integration), and ethical competencies (responsible use) (Darling-Hammond et al. 2017, 15-32).

Adapt teaching and evaluation through pedagogical redesign

Universities must update their pedagogical and evaluation methodologies to incorporate ethical use of GAI. This means redesigning tasks to require critical thinking, analysis, and application of concepts in novel contexts, rather than tasks that AI can easily complete.

Empirical justification: Concern about technological dependence and loss of critical skills (64.3% of mentions) underscores the need to redesign evaluation strategies.

Practical implementation: Adoption of frameworks like "Six Assessment Redesign Pivotal Strategies (SARPS)" that privilege processes over products and emphasize specifically human capabilities (García-Peñalvo 2024, 145-167).

Defend academic integrity and rigor

It is crucial to establish clear and transparent policies about GAI use to maintain high academic standards. Concerns about plagiarism and misuse must be addressed, promoting use that complements and does not replace student intellectual effort.

Empirical justification: 76.7% of faculty identified academic integrity as an essential aspect for institutional policies, confirming its priority.

Practical implementation: Development of frameworks that distinguish between ethical human-AI collaboration and inappropriate dependence, establishing clear criteria for evaluating intellectual originality (International Center for Academic Integrity 2021).

Guarantee equity and fair access

GAI implementation should not widen the digital divide. Institutions must strive to ensure that all students and staff have access to necessary tools, preventing technology from becoming a factor of inequality.

Empirical justification: 56.7% of faculty identified equity in access as a main ethical challenge, while 46.7% considered equitable access essential in institutional policies.

Practical implementation: Development of programs that address multiple dimensions of the digital divide: technological access, digital literacy, and cultural capital for effective navigation of AI systems (Jenkins et al. 2009, 34-52).

Prioritize ethics and data protection

Robust ethical frameworks must be created that address privacy, algorithmic bias, and protection of student data. Policies must be aligned with regulations like the EU AI Act and UNESCO recommendations.

Empirical justification: 56.7% of faculty identified data privacy and security as a main ethical challenge, while

70% considered informed consent essential in institutional policies.

Practical implementation: Establishment of protocols that include principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy, justice, and transparency, with specific policies on student data collection and use (Florida et al. 2018, 689-707).

Foster interdisciplinary collaboration

Successful GAI implementation requires collaboration between educators, technologists, administrators, ethics experts, and students. Sharing best practices between institutions and disciplines is vital as technology evolves.

Empirical justification: Although only 3.3% explicitly mentioned collective work, qualitative analysis revealed need for collaborative frameworks to address GAI implementation complexity.

Practical implementation: Creation of interdisciplinary committees with diverse representation, clear mandates, and authority to influence institutional policies, complemented by participation in professional networks and research consortiums (Beetham and Sharpe 2019, 201-223).

Promote a human-centered approach

Technology must serve pedagogical and humanistic objectives, not the reverse. The goal is to augment human capabilities, not replace them. A balance must be maintained between technological innovation and human contact, which is irreplaceable in education.

Empirical justification: Concern about loss of critical and creative skills (64.3%) evidences the need to maintain centrality of human judgment in educational processes.

Practical implementation: Design of educational experiences that privilege meaningful human interaction, using AI to create more time and space for these interactions without replacing them (Shneiderman 2022, 78-95).

Develop a solid and contextualized pedagogical framework

Instead of uncritical adoption, GAI integration must be guided by a clear pedagogical framework. Proposals like "Learning Pathways" in the Latin American context seek to integrate technology in a way that is culturally relevant and pedagogically sound.

Empirical justification: Variability in observed GAI applications (from research to bibliographic references) suggests need for structured pedagogical frameworks that guide contextualized use.

Practical implementation: Development of frameworks that consider socioeconomic characteristics of student population, available infrastructure, local regulatory frameworks, and institutional pedagogical traditions.

Evaluate and improve continuously

Policies and practices must be regularly reviewed and evaluated to adapt to rapid technology evolution and its impact on education. This implies a continuous cycle of diagnosis, design, implementation, and evaluation.

Empirical justification: Low knowledge of existing institutional policies (10%) and rapid technological evolution confirm the need for continuous evaluation and updating mechanisms.

Practical implementation: Establishment of monitoring systems that include pedagogical effectiveness, ethical impact, equity, sustainability, and user satisfaction, using quantitative and qualitative methods (Galindo Cuesta 2024).

Toward a pedagogy of human-AI collaboration

Responsible implementation of GAI in higher education requires development of a new pedagogy that recognizes human-AI collaboration as a fundamental competency of the 21st century. This pedagogy must maintain centrality of human judgment while leveraging AI's computational capabilities to enrich learning experiences.

Empirical findings confirm that faculty are navigating this transition intuitively, but require structured frameworks that allow them to maximize GAI benefits while mitigating its risks. The diversity of observed applications—from class development to rubric creation—demonstrates both potential and need for systematic guidance.

The empowered faculty member in this context is not one who technically masters AI tools, but one who understands how to integrate them critically and creatively into their pedagogical practice, always maintaining student integral formation as the central objective. This conceptualization aligns with empirical evidence showing that faculty especially value academic integrity and continuous professional development as central elements of institutional policies.

Implications for institutional policy

Results of this research have direct implications for institutional policy development at multiple levels:

Strategic level

Institutions must develop clear visions about AI's role in their educational mission, establishing principles that guide long-term decision-making. Evidence that only 10% of faculty know existing institutional policies suggests urgent need for communication and socialization of normative frameworks.

Operational level

Significant investments are required in technological infrastructure, professional development programs, and technical support systems. Identified demand for continuous training (76.7%) must translate into dedicated resources and structured programs.

Regulatory level

Institutions must establish clear policies on acceptable AI use, procedures for evaluating new tools, and mechanisms for responding to academic integrity violations. High valuation of informed consent (70%) suggests need for specific protocols for transparency in AI use.

Study limitations

This study presents several limitations that must be considered in interpreting results:

Sample limitation: The sample concentrates on a single faculty of a specific university, which may limit generalization of results to other institutional and disciplinary contexts.

Temporal limitation: Data were collected at a specific moment of rapid technological evolution, so perceptions and uses may have changed significantly.

Methodological limitation: The study is based primarily on participant self-report, which may introduce social desirability biases or inaccuracies in describing actual practices.

Contextual limitation: Findings reflect the specific Latin American context and may not be directly transferable to other cultural or regulatory contexts.

Future research directions

Results of this study suggest several directions for future research:

Longitudinal studies that document evolution of faculty perceptions and practices with GAI over time.

Comparative research between different academic disciplines to identify specific needs and strategies by knowledge area.

Implementation studies that evaluate effectiveness of different approaches to faculty training and institutional policy development.

Student impact research that examines effects of GAI integration on learning processes and competency development.

Cultural and linguistic analysis of GAI implementation in non-English speaking contexts, developing models adapted to Global South realities.

Conclusions

This research confirms that empowering faculty in the GAI era does not mean loading them with more technological tasks, but recognizing their irreplaceable role as knowledge mediators, learning designers, and guarantors of educational meaning. Empirical data collected validate the need for a systematic and contextualized approach that addresses both opportunities and challenges of GAI integration in higher education.

The presented decalogue, grounded in empirical evidence and theoretical analysis, offers a comprehensive framework for guiding responsible GAI implementation, emphasizing that success is not measured by technological adoption but by strengthening pedagogical practice and improving educational outcomes. Findings confirm that faculty especially value academic integrity, continuous professional development, and informed consent as central elements of any institutional policy.

Evidence presented demonstrates that there is a significant gap between recognition of GAI's ethical importance and knowledge of specific normative frameworks. This gap represents both a challenge and an opportunity for higher education institutions seeking to implement these technologies responsibly.

The future of education is not built with replacement of human by artificial, but with creation of intelligent synergies that leverage the best of both worlds: AI's computational capacity and educators' wisdom, creativity, and humanity. In this future, the empowered faculty member becomes the architect of learning experiences that prepare students not only to use technology, but to live full lives and contribute constructively to society.

The presented research contributes to the growing body of knowledge on responsible AI implementation in education, providing specific empirical evidence from the Latin American context and a practical framework for institutions seeking to navigate this technological transformation ethically and effectively.

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Appendix A: Questionnaire on use and perceptions of generative artificial intelligence in higher education

Knowledge about generative artificial intelligence

1. Assessment of knowledge about GAI:

Question: On a scale of 1 to 5, what is your current level of knowledge about generative artificial intelligence and its application in education?

Response options: 1 (None) - 5 (Expert)

Previous experience with GAI

2. Previous use of GAI tools:

Question: Have you previously used generative artificial intelligence tools in your teaching practice? Response options: Yes / No

3. Detail of tools used:

Question: If yes, which ones have you used and for what specific purposes? Response type: Open

Ethical perceptions

4. Ethical challenges of GAI use:

Question: What do you consider to be the main ethical challenges associated with the use of AI in education? Check the options that are relevant to you.

Response options: [List of possible ethical challenges such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, technological dependence, etc.]

Importance of ethical consideration

5. Importance of ethics in GAI:

Question: On a scale of 1 to 5, how important do you think ethical consideration is in the use of AI in education?

Response options: 1 (Not at all important) - 5 (Extremely important)

Knowledge of existing policies

6. Knowledge of policies on ethical use of AI:

Question: Are you aware of any policies on ethical use of AI at the college or university? Response options: Yes / No

7. Detail of known policies:

Question: What aspects does the policy you know cover? Response type:

Open

Contribution to institutional policy

8. Essential aspects for institutional policies:

Question: What aspects do you consider essential to include in an institutional policy on the ethical use of AI?

Response options: [Space for open response or list of options to check]